

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING ART, ARTISTIC CREATIVITY AND ART THERAPY IN PREVENTING AGGRESSION IN CHILDREN

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Annotation.

This article focuses on the importance of art therapy as an effective tool against children's aggression, which is one of today's urgent problems, and its important aspects. revealed.

Keywords.

art therapy methods, drawing, image, color, psychological protection, aggressive behavior, correction of aggression, individuality.

If literature, art and culture live, the nation and the people, the whole humanity will live peacefully!

Sh. M. Mirziyoyev

INTRODUCTION

Today, aggressive behavior is the most common among children. Researchers say that the number of children who exhibit aggressive behavior is increasing every year. Sometimes it is difficult to work with them, and often adults do not know how to fight. It is known that in modern pedagogy and psychology, great attention is paid to the development of methods of prevention and reduction of aggression. Art therapy is often used as one of the effective methods of working with children who have emotional difficulties in behavior. So L.D. According to Lebedeva, "corrective possibilities of art therapy give the child practically unlimited opportunities for self-expression and self-knowledge and self-affirmation in the product of his creativity"

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Usually, the use of art therapy is indispensable for emotional disorders, communication difficulties, as well as a low level of motivation for activities. V.A. Doskin writes: "Difficulties in communication, isolation, low interest in peers, or excessive shyness, art therapy allows children to join the group and facilitate the communication process without changing the individual nature of their activity" [2,

15]. In this regard, the analysis of the work experience of pedagogues-psychologists in recent years has been confirmed in practice, and they were awarded O.M. Rudnitskaya, E.V. Okhotnikova, E.L. Shustova, I.A. Ponamoreva, I.V. Sevostyanova, V.P. Mukhina, E.N. Ganekin, L.N. We can cite the Korsakovs as an example. Let's briefly reveal the possibilities of art therapy methods. Many preschool psychologists use the method of art therapy through painting in psycho-corrective practice. This method gives positive results when working with children with various problems. In isotherapy, drawing images are a means of psychological protection for children and help them in problematic situations. Isotherapy includes various methods. For example, through the drawings of children, it helps to identify their main problems and negative situations that affect children. It will be possible to identify situations that disturb the child with projective drawings and different drawing methods used both in a group and individually. Isotherapy provides great opportunities not only for self-expression in children, but also for the development of fantasy and positive emotions. In addition, it has a positive effect on the climate in the group, increases the self-esteem of children, helps to model problem situations, expands and forms the ability to express oneself. Isotherapy allows children to express their negative feelings and not remember negative situations in communication with other children. Also, this method is a means of identifying emotions in the development of positive interpersonal relationships between children and adults. Art therapy thus has its main meaning as a type of psychocorrection. It can be seen that it affects children's creativity and increases their imagination. It helps to harmonize the image of the world and strengthen the psychological health of children.

DISCUSSION

According to known studies, the figures of A. Hill, E. Adamson (Great Britain), E. Kremer, M. Huntoon, D. Jones, R. Ault (USA) and others stand out from the artistic environment as pioneers of Western art therapy. . In particular, Adrian Hill is best known for being one of the first to use the word "art therapy" to describe his work with patients in post-war British hospitals. Adrian Hill is the author of the book "Visual Art Against Disease" (1945) and the initiator of the organization of art workshops in the institutions of the National Health System. From 1946, Adamson, another English artist who began to work in a psychiatric hospital, began to hold classes with patients based on the open art workshop he created.

When we turn to creativity, we are deliberately giving it an opportunity to survive, not to get away from pain, but in art therapy it is also very important to adapt to any situation through creativity. Creativity allows you to find

paradoxical⁶⁸ solutions literally out of nothing, thereby contributing to personal self-awareness and growth. It is a rejection of stereotypical ways of thinking and acting, which helps to develop creative flight, fantasy, which means crossing the boundaries. After all, it's no secret that there are very few people who think creatively, because in the process of life, each person has an image that corresponds to the environment in which he was born, which may have prohibitions and limits. Norms, awkward situations and yes many other moments in the womb, they can "delete" the matrix that is inherent in a person from the very beginning. Therapy awakens creativity in man, and man awakens in creativity, and this is necessary to survive in an ever-changing world. The more advanced the society, the less pleasure there is. If we dwell on the differences between art and other activities, the difference is that it does not set practical and pragmatic goals. In science, a person strives for accuracy, correctness, understanding of the essence, confirmation with various theories, art is holistic in its essence and at the same time dreamy, glittering with its fantasies and colors.

Images and sounds cannot cause pain or injury, art can make a person feel and see the world in a completely different way, feel himself and his experiences, evaluate himself differently. Everyone has their own story. There are funny and sad moments in this story. There are situations that you really want to remember, relive, maybe think about anew, but access to them is behind the "seven locks", that is, internal anomalous feelings.

RESULTS

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⁶⁸Paradox (ancient Greek prados - "unexpected; strange", another Greek pyara - "against, contrary" and another Greek dōla - "opinion; representation; hypothesis") in a broad sense - statement, opinion, reasoning. generally accepted opinion and seem illogical or contrary to common sense. A paradox arises when two mutually exclusive (opposite) statements can be proved to the same extent.

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RESULTS

Art therapy is the key to unlocking a person's creative potential, releasing their hidden energy reserves, and ultimately finding the best ways to solve their problems. Everything related to creativity implies fun and creativity. If the client is not a professional, and there is a rule in art therapy - you can work in pairs, but the client does not have to be a professional, then the creative process becomes a kind of game. In fact, in English-speaking countries, this approach to art therapy, as a rule, is called "therapeutic fine art" (therapeutic art), "fine art as therapy" (as art therapy), "healing art" (healing art) and has been used as a form of psychotherapeutic practice or art psychotherapy. Although therapeutic visual creativity and artistic psychotherapy are two sides of the same phenomenon or two different forms of realizing the therapeutic potential of visual activity, they have a number of fundamental differences, primarily related to the use of different therapeutic synogenic⁶⁹ factors. Preschool age has the richest opportunities for developing creative abilities. But unfortunately, these opportunities gradually

⁶⁹ Sanogenik fikrlash (lotincha sanus "sog'lom" - boshqa yunoncha "kelib chiqishi; rivojlanish" dan) - his-tuyg'ularni boshqarishga qaratilgan fikrlash.

disappear over time, so it is necessary to use them as effectively as possible during the preschool age, when children are very inquisitive and have a great desire to learn the world around them. At a time when life is becoming more colorful and complex today, art therapy is not about the usual actions, but about mobility, flexibility of thinking, quick orientation and adaptation to new conditions, different problems, in order not to miss the sensitive period for the development of creativity. requires a creative approach to solving. Based on the experience of developing the creative abilities of older preschool children, we have chosen art therapy methods and tools that fully and effectively activate the child's resource potential.

Art therapy in education is a systematic innovation, which is characterized by:

- set of theoretical and practical ideas, new technologies;
- social, psychological and diversity of communication with pedagogical events;
- independence (separation) from other components of pedagogical reality (educational processes, management, etc.);
- ability to integrate and change.

Recommendations for correcting aggressive behavior in children. Aggressive behavior is one of the most common among children. Because this is an easy way for a child to achieve a goal. Aggression is an act that goes against the norms and rules of the existence of people in society, harms the objects of attack (animate and inanimate), causes physical and moral harm to people, or psychological discomfort to them. is a motivated destructive behavior. Aggressiveness is a personality trait expressed in readiness for aggression. Another reason for the appearance of aggression in children can be anxiety and fear of attack. This child is motivated by the fact that he has probably been subjected to physical punishment, insults, insults several times in his life. In this case, first of all, it is necessary to talk to the parents, to explain to them the possible reasons and consequences of such behavior. Sometimes aggression is a way to attract the attention of others, the reason for which is an unsatisfied need for connection and affection. Aggression can also act as a form of protest against limiting some of the child's natural desires and needs. For example, the need for movement, vigorous activity. Teachers, who do not want to take into account the child's natural need for movement, do not know that preschoolers and elementary school students cannot do one thing for a long time, that activity is physiologically characteristic of them. They artificially and completely unnaturally try to turn off the activity of children, force them to sit and stand against their will. Usually, such actions of an adult are like twisting a spring.

The more you press it, the faster it will return to its previous state. They often cause indirect, if not direct, aggression. Before trying to correct the child's aggressive behavior, try to understand its reasons. Often, a child's aggression is a form of protest against the actions and behavior of adults. Think about whether you spend enough time with him, how much you communicate with him. Perhaps the child feels that you lack attention and is trying to attract him in ways that attract him. The ideological platform of the inventors of art therapy from the artistic environment is an innovative art pedagogy, the concept of education and educational influence on the individual through art, which is often combined with psychoanalytic views of visual art as a conductor of unconscious impulses.

Travesti - "downgrading, humiliation, mockery". Through art, a person can make fun of things that people cannot overcome, that cause fear. By modeling his fears, drawing a picture of what scares him, a person is able to understand the root of these fears. Sometimes, for example, it is easy to draw a huge bear going on a hunt as a small and funny weirdo. Art is truly a wonderful thing and it is truly therapeutic, playing with words, music, paints, costumes, masks, clay and many other attributes of art to create a hologram of the human image, and the essence of the problem. able to find So feel it, accept it and let it go. Art teaches survival and acceptance of life. Art heals, that is, it restores a person to wholeness.

Art therapy is unique and indispensable in cases where the verbal method is impossible, it is a special language of self-expression through art. Art therapy sometimes becomes the only way to "connect" between a person and society, between a client and a counselor. All languages are used in art therapy (body, sound, etc.). Creativity itself is inextricably linked with the concept of pleasure as a process. Creativity, by its very nature, cannot cause pain, but it can lead to experience. Because it is absolutely impossible to forget or suppress trauma. But you can survive, assimilate⁷⁰, accept and let go. Therefore, art therapy is recognized as the most painless way to solve problems.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that, based on the experience of pedagogues and psychologists and representatives of other fields, it is important to use the most effective art therapy methods when creating a program for the prevention of aggressive behavior in children. In the process of art therapy, the child gets a valuable experience of positive changes. Gradually, there will be deep self-knowledge, self-acceptance, harmonization of development, personal growth.

⁷⁰ In the process of assimilation, the accumulation of substances used as a source of energy for the growth, development and renewal of the organism is ensured.

Communication, which is important in this work, is used as the basis of effective interaction. Usually, art therapy is one of the areas of psychotherapy with art, along with music therapy, dance-movement therapy and drama therapy, and is a type of professional activity or service performed by specially trained personnel.

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